

Review

Bacteriophage and Phage-Therapy: An Alternative to Antibiotics

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Abstract— Bacteriophages are known for a century but their use in therapy to cure bacterial infection is still unknown. The working on bacteriophage investigation started about a century ago with their discovery by the English microbiologist Twort in 1915. The continuous growth of resistance in bacteria for various diseases and infections has caused renewing in bacteriophage therapy against bacterial infections. Lytic bacteriophages are those bacteriophages that can kill bacteria that are resistant to antibiotics by the end of their lytic cycle. Bacteriophages use proteins for the lysis of bacteria, termed as the Holin-lysine system. Research is going on globally on therapeutic uses of bacteriophages as less is known about phage therapy to combat bacterial diseases and infections. This therapy has attracted many scientists as difficulty in curing bacterial infection is at the peak. This difficulty is arising mainly in antibiotic-resistance bacteria in contemporary medicine.

Keywords— Holin lysis system, Bacteriophage, Phage therapy, Antibiotic-resistance bacteria, MDR, chemotherapy

I. INTRODUCTION

Bacteriophages were discovered by an English Microbiologist name Twort in 1915, but depth was known when it was published in a journal by Felix d'Herelle. He independently discovered bacteriophage and is considered as the father of phage therapy while working on patients suffering from dysentery. Bacteriophages which are informally known as Phage are small viruses that are parasites to bacteria. They have the potential to infect and replicate within a bacterial cell. They kill the bacteria while they do not affect the human or any other cell lines from another organism[1]. A new bacteriophage journal was introduced in early by Alexander sulakvelidze. He defined bacteriophages as "the most ubiquitous organisms on earth. They play an important role in maintaining microbial balance on earth[2]. With the advancements in antibiotics, the sulfa drugs, and the discovery of penicillin in the years 1930 and 1940 respectively, working on phage was significantly reduced. The therapeutic use of bacteriophage was masked by other traditional treatments, the use of antibiotics, and chemotherapy. It was not accepted by people and the medical community[1]. However, by contrast, research and development were going on in some European countries like Poland, the Soviet Union, Germany, and to some lesser extent India. The effortless use of bacteriophages was still in prominent use and various investigation into phage therapy ran beneath. Over the last decade, investigators are made to reconsider this research on phage as multidrug-resistant

bacteria are growing at a high rate. Phage therapy may compensate for unforeseen complications of chemotherapy such as the presence of multidrug resistance or substituted microbes[3], [4].

Bacteriophages have been used in the early years for bacterial infections like *Shigella dysenteriae* in 1919 and other bacterial diseases caused by *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus*, *Proteus*, and *Stenotrophomonas*. Recent reports indicate that proper administration of phage leads to the treatment of many lethal diseases caused by gram-negative as well as gram-positive bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, and *Salmonella spp.*, and *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* respectively[5], [6]. Hirshfield Institute of Immunology and Experimental Therapy in Wroclaw is a phage therapy center that offers patients therapies against all these diseases although the center does not offer therapies against the diseases caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Haemophilus influenza*. Combinations of phage strains are used to enhance the therapeutic actions and to reduce the risk of resistance to phage therapy by the bacteria. Many different types of bacteriophages have been discovered and their morphology has been described correctly. There is a total of 6000 different bacteriophages, including 6196 bacterial and 88 archaeal viruses[7]. For good results and a better understanding of the therapy, the strains of phage particles must be known before an experiment. Bacteriophages are classified according to their Morphology, their genome, their nucleic acid whether DNA or RNA, their specific host, the place they live, and most importantly their life cycle[1].

In this review, we are going to talk about the history of phage therapy or its historical background, inflation in antibiotics usage in the 20th century giving rise to reappraisal and recent interest in phage therapy for MDR bacteria, the working of phage or their life cycle for killing bacteria called as the Hollin-lysin system[5], the adaptive and the specific immune responses against bacteriophages during the therapy, phage therapy vs. Antibiotic therapy, phage cocktails, advantages, disadvantages, limitations of phage therapy as well as antibiotics.

II. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Introduction to bacteriophages was given by Ernest Hanbury Hankins, a British Bacteriologist to the United Province and

Central Province of India while testing waters of Indian rivers Yamuna and Ganga. He found that the water samples contained biological principles that destroy the cultures of cholera-inducing bacteria. His work got published in French in *Annals of the Pasteur Institute*[8], [9]. The very first documented clinical use of phage was done in Paris in 1919 by d'Herelle; he successfully used phage to treat patients suffering from bacterial dysentery and coined the term "bacteriophages" (literal meaning "bacteria eater"). Despite all of his efforts and successful trials, his experiments were said to be controlled badly and the research was stopped[3]. Despite all this d'Herelle did not stop working on his experiments and continued with his trials. d'Herelle introduced the use of bacteriophage in therapeutic medicines and did experimental trials all over the world. From his experience all over the world, he introduced intravenous phage for invasive infection and compiled his work in 1931. He also did trials of phage in the Punjab region of India on phage therapy for the treatment of cholera which involved a group of more than 100 patients and 73 experimental subjects, he observed a 90% of mortality rate and around 74% lethality in the control cohort and appropriately 5% in the experimental cohort[10].

In Belgium, Bruynoghe and Maisin, however, have published the first paper on the clinical application of phage, using bacteriophage in infusing the *Staphylococcal spp.* phagi near the base of the cutaneous boils to treat cutaneous furuncles and carbuncles. They identified clear clinical signs within 48 hours of pain, swelling, and fever reduction in treated patients. Many complications and mistakes were made during these early trials which were generally due to lack of knowledge about the biological nature of phage[1]. A phage summit was held in Key Biscayne, Florida which was the first important international gathering devoted only to phage biology and it was attended by more than 350 countries in August 2004. Pakistan in around the 1970s, some experimental trials were done in the treatment of cholera from the strains taken from USSR which was sponsored by WHO[5], [11]. They concluded that the treatment of cholera is far effective when done with tetracycline (antibiotics) rather than phage, but they also observed that anti-cholera phage reduces almost all the vibrio causing it without affecting the patient's cell lines. Therefore, phage might be a good and very useful study instrument[12].

Recently, phage therapy has attracted many of the scientists and researchers. On September 21, 2016, United Nations General Assembly found bacterial infection a threat to the nation's health. The assembly discussed the damages and extent of bacterial infections and summoned not to only rely

on antibiotics against bacterial infections but also to lay emphasis on Phage Therapy as an alternative strategy for prophylaxis and its use in therapeutic medicine. With major advancement and discovery in Analytical tools such as Next Generation Sequencing and Electron Microscopy, etc., the phage biology is highlighted. With clinical trials in humans and animals, it is reaching a wave of success[3].

A. Mechanism of Phage Therapy Against Multi-Drug Resistance Bacteria by Phage-Derived Lytic Proteins

Globally, antibiotic-resistant bacteria have taken a significant place. Antibiotics have brought about revolutionary changes around the world for centuries. But, due to many demerits, medical units are shifting their treatment towards phage therapy for serious bacterial infections. The demerits include global use of antibiotics are overuse of antibiotics in medical settings, availability and use of antibiotics without prescriptions in some countries, and administration of antibiotics in huge quantities in livestock. Due to which there is now an increasing number of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains which is a serious problem in medicine right now. This has led to the development of an alternative for treating serious infections caused by MDR (Multi-Drug Resistance) Bacteria, Lytic Phage Therapy. The important fact is these strains are not resistant to phage lysis mechanisms. The antibiotic-resistant bacteria are lysed at the end of the lytic phase. The phage uses mainly 2 components for the lysis mechanism to destroy the bacterial cell wall and to release the virions[5], [13], [14].

During the lysis of the bacterial host, two main types of proteins are used by most phage organisms. One is a transmembrane protein Holin and the other one is endolysin (lysin), which is a peptidoglycan cell wall hydrolase, both synergize with each other. Bacterial lysis is essential to release the viral progeny from infected cells; studies on phage lytic mechanisms have helped a lot in phage therapies. Lytic bacteriophages use proteins or their small DNA or RNA genome which encode single proteins to stop peptidoglycan synthesis[5], [15], [16].

Both the proteins trigger the lysis of the peptidoglycan layer in the bacterial cell wall. The protein Holin acts as a time-recorder or clock during the whole lytic cycle. It remains in the cell membrane till phage assembly or viral assembly. At the end of the lytic cycle, they trigger perforation in the host cytoplasmic membrane and thus help endolysin to enter in the peptidoglycan layer of the host membrane. Holin and lysin

protein are specific to specific phage-type. There are huge structural and biochemical variabilities between phage species and conservation in phage species is less. Holin in every phage species has a minimum one hydrophobic (water-hating) domain, Transmembrane domain (TMD), and C-terminal hydrophilic(water-loving) domain. It has a high electric charge. Holins are of 3 types according to the number of TMDs. Class I, Class II, and Class III. The Class I protein has more than 95 amino acids in length, these holins have 3 TMDs. They belong to *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteriophage p68 hol115 protein and *E. coli* phage lambda S105 protein. Similarly, classes II and III have two and one TMDs respectively with 65 to 95 amino acid residues in length. Class II is represented by Lambdoid phage 21 S protein and *Clostridium perfringens* bacteriophage 3626 hol13626 and class III by phage CP26F holin[5].

Cell wall degradation is done by phage endolysin. Endolysin alone can cause cell wall degradation but holin cannot act alone. Endolysin shows the activities of amidase, glycosidase or lytic transglycosylate as well as endopeptidase to kill the bacterial cell by murein destruction[5]. Endolysins work rapidly and are potent contradictory to holin protein. They are inactive against eukaryotic cells. They also differ according to their structures like the ones which work against gram-negative bacteria have different structures than the ones which work against gram-positive bacteria because the gram-negative bacteria is surrounded by an outer layer which makes the access to the peptidoglycan layer restricted from the outside.

It is necessary to terminate the phage lytic mechanism on a precise time which is done by this holin-lysin system. A dual start model explains this termination on a precise time point, the time of lysis of bacteria is dependent on an open reading frame which governs the regulation between holin and its opposite anti-holin at a translational level. Once the holin has worked, it initiates and gives access to endolysin to enter periplasmic space and degrade the peptidoglycan layer[17]–[19]. Research is going on to use a combination of antibiotics and phage therapy mechanisms to combat and sabotage bacterial infections. It has been demonstrated in in-vitro and ex-vivo colon model in *C. difficile*[20], [21].

B. Immunological response induced by phage therapy in the human host

It is crucial to determine how the host body reacts to the entry of any foreign particle whether it a bacteriophage or any

foreign particle. Studies about phage therapy and its immunological responses are very essential as it can carry a risk to the host. The immune response against bacteriophages depends upon many factors like (a) injection site (b) localization of infection (c) the route of phage administration. Both adaptive and innate immune responses are triggered when bacterial pathogens are administered intravenously. Phage is also able to induce specific antibodies against them, which usually inhibit phage effectiveness to lyse the targeted bacteria in vivo. However, bacteriophages are already present in a healthy human body in its microbiota, studies are being conducted for evaluation of activities of bacteriophages on the microbiota. It implies that it could not have harmful effects on the human host, and it is not a threat to the immune system.

In a study, Lusiak-Szelachowska et al. the neutralization of patient images with PT was given. The study concluded that the way phage is administered is important because one goal is to minimize the patient's anti-phage reaction to PT. With the advancement of vaccine development, it was studied that phage is used in the development of vaccines and so, it was confirmed that phage induces innate as well as adaptive immunity. Bacteriophages are sensed by dendritic cells and thus induce innate and adaptive immunity. It can show major and strong hypersensitivity reactions[22], [23].

Another study shows that “Neutralizing Antibodies” are one of the major factors and limitations of phage therapy. But the further study by Sulakvelidze et al suggested that the development of neutralizing antibody is not a major issue in phage therapy as the kinetics of phage therapy are much faster than the host immune response. It can still be solved in three ways (a) increase phage induction (b) increase phage concentration in the phage cocktail (c) use a different type of phage as the resistance differs for different phage[5]. As phage treatment results can be seen, not only on the anti-bacterial properties of phage therapy but also on the anti-inflammatory properties, as phage treatment is a strong immunomodulator. The results are also evident.

III. EXPEDIENCY OF PHAGE THERAPY (PT)

A. Auto-dosing- While combating with bacterial infections, the phage can increase their number specifically wherever the host is located. They tend to increase their dose by themselves, so it is termed as auto-dosing.

- B. Single-dose potential-** Phage is required in single-dose giving it the advantage of replicating fast and achieve ‘active’ therapy. It is very convenient to provide a single dose during the therapy[24].
- C. Single hit kinetics-** A distinct phage is enough to lyse a single bacterium, unlike chemicals in antibiotics that are required in high amounts[25].
- D. Phage are natural products-** Public resistance applied to genetically modified organisms and antibiotics should not be applied to phage as they are natural and occur in the environment[24], [25].
- E. Phage is not antibiotics-** They do not cause evolutionary resistance in bacteria as antibiotics do. Over improper use of antibiotics in humans as well as animal diseases have caused mayhem leading to unnecessary troubles like antibiotic contamination of food. Using phage instead of antibiotics could help extend the clinical utility of antibiotics[24].
- F. Bactericidal agents-** Unlike antibiotics, the phage can kill bacteria that is they cannot gain their viability again. Antibiotics like tetracycline have permitted bacterial evolution towards resistance[24], [25].
- G. Relatively low cost-** The cost of phage production is generally low as compared to antibiotics in the pharma industry. The cost required during the discovery is also low.
- H. Narrower Resistance Induction Potential-** The relatively limited host range shown in most phases restricts the number of bacterial types from which phage resistance mechanisms may be selected.
- I. Minimal Destruction to Normal Flora-** Because of their host specificity from the capacity of a few bacterial strains to infect more seldom than a more closely associated bacterial specimen — phage has a low effect on the health safety of normal flora bacteria.

IV. DEMERITS OF PHAGE THERAPY

A. Not all phage makes a good selection for therapeutics- All phage is not suitable for therapeutics because of low absorption, distribution, and survival in situ. The use of

temperate phage is not beneficial because they can convert bacteria that are sensitive to phage to insensitive one.

- B. Low Virulence-** Some bacteriophage possesses low virulence as they do not kill the targeted organism with full efficacy.
- C. Phage is not unique medicine-** They can interact with the immune system of the host, can actively replicate, and can even evolve during usage or manufacture.
- D. Poor Pharmacokinetics-** Phage therapy limits the use of some bacteriophages that display poor pharmacokinetics such as poor adsorption, poor distributions, and survival in-situ.
- E. Transduction-** PT also limits those bacteriophages that readily transfer gene between bacteria i.e. transduction.

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Bacteriophages as antibacterial agents have very wide usage in therapeutics. They have several properties that make them suitable or better than an antibiotic. All the concerns regarding phage are manageable and can be solved with experiments and proper clinical trials through proper phage selection in the phage cocktails and better and effective formulations. Phage offers many advantages and relatively few inconveniences in an age where antibiotics resistant bacterial infections are on the rise. With scientific awareness now much greater than in early formative years, 1 phage therapy is worth a second chance in western medicine to demonstrate its real potential. Also, phage therapy has higher expectations for medical investigations than in early phage therapy.

The available literature on the use of phage and phage derived proteins as alternatives or as antibiotic supplements in the fight against bacterial infection, particularly multi-drug - resistant Bacteria, has become more promising. However, due to some controversy in the use of phage therapy due to minimum host range, immunomodulatory effects and bacterial gene transfer depicts that more advancement and a better understanding of phage bacterial, its relationship with bacteria and microbiome and human host is needed. The increased efficacy of antibacterial agents, when used together, suggested the need to treat the problem in antibiotic-resistant infections using a certainly combined phage, phage-

derived lytic proteins, bioengineered phage, and or antibiotics.

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VII. REFERENCE

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